
LEADERSHIP STYLES AS A PANACEA TO ACHIEVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

A lot has been done by researchers in recommending one style, theory, concept, system, technique, and innovation in order to alleviate the peculiar leadership problems, but despite their efforts, the problems have defiled most of the solutions. This study examines leadership styles as a panacea to organizational effectiveness. The related literature to the study was reviewed. Findings from the study showed that democratic leadership style is a tool for organizational effectiveness and that leadership impacts employees' performance significantly. Also, a participative leadership style helps improve performance among employees. Finally, solutions and recommendations were made, with emphasis on the best leadership styles that will achieve organizational effectiveness in learning organizations.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Leadership, Organisation, Achievement, Productivity.

Introduction

There are as many approaches to leadership as there are leaders, from Lewis's leadership styles framework of the 1930s to the more recent ideas about transferring national leadership. There are also many general styles, including servant and transactional leadership. Building awareness of frameworks and styles can help you develop your approach and be a more effective leader. From Mahatma Gandhi and Winston Churchill to Martin Luther King and Steve Jobs, there can be as many ways or styles to lead people as there are leaders.

The emergence of organizations sprang out of the burning desire to achieve optimum productivity. This implies that set goals cannot be realized in isolation by individuals. The organization is the individual, and the individual is the organization. To this end, the operations of any organization are dependent on the leadership and the followership, who are guided towards the achievement of the organization's desires. The aspirations of an organization ab initio hinge on the generation of high performance and the management of resources (human and material) to actualize effectiveness and efficiency.

Business people and psychologists have developed useful frameworks that describe the main ways that people lead. When you understand these frameworks, you can develop your own approach to leadership and become a more effective leader as a result. If ever there was a time in history when we should be studying the principles of leadership, it is now. Worldwide, we are facing a leadership crisis. The great need of the hour is for positive, constructive, dynamic, creative, and effective leadership.

Business, industry, government, labor, education, and the church are all starving for effective leadership. We may have many people filling administrative positions, but the need is for true leaders who are able to do the job more effectively. Every organization needs to continuously develop skills in order to achieve success. The organization is divided into leaders and followers. Civilization must experience progress, and progress depends on leadership.

Leadership can be described as:

- Knowing what to do
- Knowing why that's important and
- Knowing how to bring appropriate resources to bear all the need at hand.

Or, simply put, one who knows the way, goes the way, and shows the way. This is basically based on the fact that the development of organizations is based on careful arrangement, analysis of programs, and selection of adequate activities for success. Therefore, effective leadership drives the activities of the organization and strives to achieve them through the application of the right management principles and administrative behaviors in the quest for organizational effectiveness.

The Concept of Leadership

Many schools of thought have attributed special traits to leaders. Others have argued that leaders are products of their eras; fortunately, they happened to be born at a time that provided fruitful

opportunities. Every group distinguishes between the role of a commander and the role of a follower. One could reasonably state that the function of the is to modify or direct control the action of a particular group; this is more or less traditionally associated with executives, managers, supervisors, foremen, psychologists, etc. Whenever people come together in small groups, whether the membership is political, social, or contraction management, several things occur with remarkable regularity: people begin to exchange ideas, opinions, views, and interpretations. They interact and influence each other in positive and negative ways, e.g., in monthly meetings, and because of this exchange, their behavior is affected in certain ways.

Every organization is set up to achieve specific goals and objectives. In its attempts to achieve those goals, each organization should endeavor to acquire the necessary inputs in the right quantity and quality. Although the objectives of an organization could be determined by the nature of the inputs required, the most important and critical of all the inputs is human resources. After all, it is the human resources that process all other resources (inputs) in order to achieve the end results (output) in the form of goods and services. Leadership is the process of using others to achieve organizational objectives. According to Okoroma (2000), leadership is a means of direction and a product of interactions. It is an input into an organization that involves interpersonal influence as one initiates structures and acts that result in a consistent pattern of group interaction aimed at productivity and individual fulfillment (Chike-Okoli, 2009).

Reviewing the above, the leadership process involves directing and influencing people to willingly carry out tasks for the achievement of a group goal. It incorporates the relationship between a person singled out to coordinate the affairs of a group and the task to be accomplished. The central theme of leadership is getting things accomplished through people (Sapru, 2013). It can be accessed from the following perspectives: what the leader has to do, how he does it, the reason for doing what he does, and what he will do. From all indications, leadership is the apex and center of activities in every organization. These activities metamorphose into productivity through proper coordination and direction. This is evident in Chike-Okoli (2008), which posits that leadership can motivate employees through the following medium:

1. Job enrichment, security and satisfaction; and
2. Provision of good working environment and condition

It is pertinent to know that every organization therefore has certain basic functions to perform: planning, organizing, integrating, and controlling. Integration is one of the functions of an organization; therefore, the elements of leadership and motivation become very paramount. If leadership is such an important factor, the critical issue is therefore: what makes a great leader? The tempting answer is great followers. Therefore, leadership can be defined simply as the art of influencing the behavior of a group of people so that their activities are directed towards achieving the specific goals and objectives of that group. Allen (1964) defined leadership as “the work a manager performs to cause people to take effective action”. He identifies five main activities that are associated with leadership:

- i. Management Decision-making
- ii. Management communication
- iii. Motivation.

- iv. Selecting people and
- v. Developing

In any society or organization, effective leadership is essential to the achievement of results. This is why those who aspire to leadership position should imbibe qualities that could assist the organization achieving its goals and objectives. The degree of achieving corporate goals and objectives could depend on how effective a leader could be. An effective leader is that person in authority who is capable of directing the available resources using various techniques and skills at different times and levels in achieving results more effectively and economically. Effectiveness in leadership is mostly determined by the three main forces:

(a) Forces in the leadership

This include those personal value system i.e. how strongly he feels that individuals should have a share in decisions which affect them, or to what extend does he allow each officer charged with every responsibility to assume the burden of taking that decision.

(b) Forces in his subordinates

Does he consider individual difference in his subordinates?

Does he consider their motivational needs?

What of individual expectations from the organization.

Subordinates expectation on how the leader should manage the organization.

Environment pressure from the organization, work group and individuals within

(c) Forces in the situation

The organization, pressure of time.

Effective Leadership

Effectiveness implies having power to produce a required or desired effect. An effective leader is one who has integrity, initiative, creativity, intelligence, charisma and competence to carry people along. Effective leadership is characterised by a strong drive for responsibility and task completion, vigor and persistence in pursuit of goals, venture some and originality in problem solving (Stogdill, 1970 in Okoroma, 2000). For a leader to be effective, there must be followers and situations. It is also worthy to note that the quality of a leader in an organization makes or mars the success. Abdussamii (2014) identified the following qualities of an effective leader:

1. Knowledge, trustworthiness, honesty, responsibility and accountability;
2. Ability, capacity, genuineness, firmness, fairness justice, initiative, creative and assertive;
3. Positive, foresight, modesty, clear vision, understanding and broad mindedness;
4. Information management, straight forwardness, cheerfulness, nice, accommodating, exemplary, demonstrative and practical;
5. willing to admit mistakes and ever ready for amendments;
6. Inquisitive, detailed, oriented, competitiveness and flexibility.

A leader who possesses up to half of these qualities must achieve high performance and productivity in the organisation, which ultimately confirms him an effective leader.

Organisation

Organisation is an organized group of people with a particular purpose, such as business or government department. Business Jargons (2019) defines organisation as a collection of people, who are involved in pursuing defined objectives. It could be described as a social system which comprises all formal human relationships. The organisation encompasses division of labour among employees and alignment of tasks towards the ultimate goal of the company. It could also be referred to as a managerial function that coordinates employees' activities to achieve goals. Organisation is goal oriented, which is pursued through proper planning, coordination, division of labour and authority – responsible relationship among members.

Similarly, organisation is categorized in to two groups: formal and informal organisations. Formal organisation deals with the structure of jobs and positions with specified activities and relationships created by management to attain its objectives, while informal organisation deals with relationship between the employees that relies on personal attitudes, prejudices and interests rather than procedures. The organisation referred to in this context is a formal organisation where the leader is saddled with the responsibilities of gathering and channelling activities of individuals and other resources to achieve goals.

Leadership styles for organizational effectiveness

Several researchers have investigated into organisational leadership to ascertain the styles and theories that make a leader distinct from other leaders. But it seems that there is no one style that is acclaimed the best. Leadership style being the behavior, techniques, strategies and methods leaders exhibit in coordinating their followers or subordinates differ according to individuals. No two leaders are the same, each one operates and carries the same functions from different perspectives. The function of a leader is to co-ordinate a group towards realizing the organisations goal. Chike – Okoli (2009) avers that the function of a leader is to influence the group towards the achievement of group goals by planning, organizing, directing and integrating the institutional demands and the needs of members in a way that will be both productive and individually fulfilling. This is to say that leadership style of an individual depends on the nature of the leader, the nature of the followers and the nature of the organisation.

There are different types of leadership style namely autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, laissez-faire leadership, charismatic, bureaucratic, task – oriented, relation oriented, servant, transactional and transformational leadership styles.

Autocratic leadership is characterized by individual control over the decisions and contributions of the followers. He is full of authority and command without consideration of the subordinates except the organisation. The leader is a dictator, arrogant and does not take corrections nor shares ideas with his subordinates.

Democratic leadership accommodates every member of the organisation. It gives room for participation of the employees in the activities of the organisation, including decision making. The employees are satisfied because their ideas, suggestions and opinions are given considerations.

Laissez faire is a carefree attitude of the leader to his subordinate and the organisational activities. No form of control is exercised in pursuit of the organisation's goals. Complete

freedom and happiness of the group at the expense of the organisation is his interest. The achievement of the goals depends on the commitment of the subordinate. It is also known as delegative leadership.

Charismatic leadership depends on the possession of some natural traits like personality trait, physical built and other abilities. Such leaders are said to be born to rule or naturally great men. They lead people to accomplish tasks as a result of their qualities which endear them to the people. They are liked, respected and appreciated because of the manner in which they operate. This style of leadership may have negative influence on the organisation.

Transactional leadership promotes compliance by followers through rewards and punishments. It focuses on supervision, organisation and performance. This type of leadership pays attention to followers' works in order to find faults and deviations. It is only effective during emergency situations.

Transformational leadership deals with team work to identify needed change and create vision. It enhances motivation, morale and job performance of followers through a variety of ways. A transformational leader inspires followers and makes them committed to their jobs.

Based on the above, a leader cannot be effective with only one style and theory of leadership. Effective leadership will imply a combination of all the styles and theories, applying them at the appropriate times. This approach is called "synthetic". An effective leader should lead the organisation to greater heights with the adoption of a variety of styles. Okoroma (1999) identified six elements crucial for effective leadership – (i) selfless service, (ii) compassion for people (iii) show of love (iv) reasonableness and moderation v) strength and courage and vi) honesty and purpose. Despite the above elements identified by Okoroma, Duggan (2019) suggests the following factors for leadership effectiveness – motivation, team building, change, mentoring, clarity and good communication.

As a matter of fact, effective leadership has a lot of hurdles to subdue to break even. The most difficult resources to manage is human resources, hence, a leader must be one endowed with the above qualities to direct the organisational activities properly. He must be intelligent, innovative; initiative, creative, always ready to accept and correct his mistakes and most of all show compassion and motivation.

Theoretical Framework

In order to properly understand the different leadership styles, a cursory look at the various leadership theories is necessary. The literatures on leadership are voluminous, and much of it is confusing and contradictory. Therefore, few shall be considered for the purpose of the research study to explain what makes an effective leader. You need to be sensitive to the needs and feelings of your team or organization. You need to support them, help them, and be concerned for their well-being. The true leader will subordinate his/her own needs to those of others. Morale and productivity are highest in group when leaders show a high degree of consideration and concern for their team.

Fair, firm and friendly is the secret, treating others as you would like to be treated play no favorites, getting a fair deal is the most important concern to employees at all levels. The effective leader has the ability to make feel good about them, giving consideration,

demonstration concern and being fair creates a strong bond between the leader and his or her team. The effective leader is team centered and a good listener.

However the early leadership concept was based on the fact that the leaders were born with the innate leadership qualities. Others attributed leadership to the nature of the physical characteristics of people. Others believed that through training of certain individuals, leaders could emerge.

1. TRADITIONAL OR GREATMAN APPROACH

This is the early approach which based leadership on the fact that leaders are born with innate leadership qualities. In other words, leadership was hereditary. A leader must have been born into the family or lineage of past leaders whose qualities of leadership are drawn from the qualities of such great man.

2. TRAIT APPROACH

Trait approach believed that personal characteristics of past successful leaders could be used as basis for determining those who may become leaders. Such traits includes: intelligence, initiative, receptiveness, vision, communicative ability, strength, bravery, sense of human understanding and supervisory ability etc.

The search for characteristics such as those listed above that would differentiate leaders from non-leaders occupied the early psychologists who studied leadership. The critical question one way want to ask would be, is it to locate one or more personality, social, physical or intellectual characteristics in individuals we generally acknowledge as leaders, that non-leaders do not possess? People like Mahatma Gandhi, Luther king, Adolf Hitler, John .F. Kennedy, Alh. Shehu Shagari, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo, Goodluck Jonathan, we may agree are individuals with utterly different characteristics. If the concept of traits were to be proved valid, there must be specific characteristics that all leaders possess. Research effort at isolating these traits resulted in a number of dead ends. For instance a review of twenty different studies identified nearly eighty leadership traits, but only five of these traits were common to four or more investigations (J.G. Geiner)-A trait approach of the study of leadership in small groups. A major movement away from trait began as early as the 1940s; leadership research from the late 40's through the mid-1960's emphasized the preferred behavioral style that leaders demonstrated.

3. BEHAVIOURAL THEORIS

These were theories proposing that specific behaviors differentiate leaders from non-leaders. There were a number of studies that looked at behavioral styles but two of these studies which were most popular are: (i) Ohio state Group and (ii) The university of Michigan Group. The Ohio state Group identified two major categories of leader behavior.

INITIATING STRUCTURE: This refers to the extent to which a leader is likely to define and structure his or her role and those of subordinates in the search for goal attainment. It includes behavior that attempt to organize work, work relationship and goal. The leaders assign group members to particular tasks, expect works to maintain definite standards of performance and emphasize the meeting of deadlines.

CONSIDERATION: this is described as the extent to which a person is likely to have job relationships that are characterized by mutual trust, respect for her followers comfort, well-being, status and satisfaction.

UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN STUDIES

These studies were similar to that of Ohio state group. They came up with two dimensions of leadership that they called “Employee oriented” and “Production oriented”.

- (a) **EMPLOYEE ORIENTED:** Leaders were those described as those emphasizing interpersonal relations, they took a personal interest in the individual differences among members.
- (b) **PRODUCTION ORIENTED:** Leader in contrast, tended to emphasize the technical or task aspect of the job. Their main concern was in accomplishing their group’s task and the group members were a means to an end.

The Michigan researchers therefore concluded that employee oriented leaders were associated with high group productivity, organization effectiveness and job satisfaction; While production-oriented leaders tend to be associated with low group productivity and low work satisfaction. Thus, they strongly favored the leaders who were employee oriented in their behavior.

MODERN APPROACH- CONTINGENCY/SITUATIONAL THEORY

The changing situation in our society today coupled with the complex nature of our organizations has called for a new approach to leadership management. It is now believed that leadership role is a function of the situation a manager finds himself. Hence, the nature of leadership can be attributed to:

- i. The nature of the group
- ii. The nature of the problem
- iii. The nature of the environment

The relationship between leadership style and effectiveness suggested that under condition ‘A’ style X would be appropriate, while style ‘Y’ would be more suitable for condition ‘B’ and style Z for condition ‘C’. But what were these conditions A, B, C, etc? It was one thing to say that leadership effectiveness was dependent on the situational condition.

There were several studies that attempted to isolate critical situational factors that affect leadership effectiveness. For example, popular moderating variables used in the development of contingency theories includes the degree of structure in the task being performed, the leader’s position power, subordinates role clarity, group norms, information availability, subordinates acceptance of leaders decision and subordinate maturity.

Several approaches to isolating key situational variables have proven more successful than others and as a result have gained under recognition. Among these are:

- (i) The autocratic-democratic continuum
- (ii) The fielder model
- (iii) Hersey and Blanchard’s situation theory
- (iv) Leader-member-Exchange theory (LMX) And
- (v) The path-Goal model.

However, for the purpose of this research review studies, path-goal theory as a derivative of leadership effectiveness shall be discussed briefly.

PATH-GOAL THEORY

It was developed by Robert House as a contingency model of leadership research that extracts key elements from the Ohio state leadership research on initiating structure and consideration and consideration and the expectancy theory of motivation.

The essence of this theory is that it is the leader's job to assist his or her followers in attaining their theory to provide the necessary direction and or support to ensure that their goals are compatible with the overall objectives of the organization. The term "Path-Goal" is derived from the belief that effective leaders clarify the path to help their followers get from where they are to the achievement.

- (i) Autocratic (Authoritarian)
- (ii) Democratic (Participatory)
- (iii) Supportive (Laissez faire conniving)

1. AUTOCRATIC LEADERSHIP

This is the type of leadership that is characterized by the use of coercion or sanction or sanction in getting his will done by the subordinates. Often he does not delegate authority. But whenever he does so he ensures that his directives are carried out without the application of external initiative. This type of leadership does not believe in wide consultation, but sometimes act on the impulse of the moment.

2. DEMOCRATIC (PARTICIPATION) LEADERSHIP

This type believes in the rule of group participation where both the leader and the lead have the opportunity of talking a critical look at issues before making decisions that would be beneficial to all. On the leadership continuum scale; democratic leadership lies somewhere between one extreme of autocratic leadership and the other extreme of supportive or laissez faire.

3. SUPPORTIVE (LAISSEZ FAIRE) LEADERSHIP

This leadership believes in the innate potentials of every individual and therefore gives room for the subordinate to exercises a lot of freedom in the execution of their responsibilities. He does not interfere much but gives support and sets good climate for his subordinates to do their best. More often than not, this leadership does not want to put blame when things go wrong since the party to the failure of that organization. The leader that takes this line of least resistance in their admiration turns out in effective. In essence this is no leadership at all.

LEADERSHIP STYLE (Managerial grid):

This is presented in a diagram below and depicted by ratios and its interpretations in leadership style.

Diagram

Rachich & Dar (1978) came up with a view that, “leadership styles have to be democratic in order to function well because staff function is specialized and finds it difficult to monopolies decision and policies”. It is mainly functional and calls for delicate balance authority to avoid in efficiency.

Therefore the leader sees himself as a colleague of the work group with certain responsibilities. The leader had to consult with subordinates and thus enable him control in services, magnitude of commitment to objective, mental and physical effort in work which is a natural as play and rest.

According to smith and powel (1988), study of the subject matter, (Leadership) quote by Stewart L. Tubb (1994) during his recent research on leadership have viewed leadership as comprising two major activities that help group and organization achieve its goal and objectives, these include:

- (a) Task function
- (b) Consideration function

The earlier involves giving and asking subordinates member for suggestion, opinion or information while the later (consideration) which has to do with moral values that improves the emotional climate or satisfaction of individual members. This is based on encouragement and support. In Nigerian public science, organization, which are non-profit organization have enough strength to provide facilities to enable employees carryout their job more efficiently and effectively depends on the leadership value i.e. the style selected in making his policy and decision.

Chuba okadigbo (1987) in his study of leadership in Nigeria said as at twenty-sixth (26th) year of National flag independence of Nigeria, leadership of a given nation must have the right constitutionalism, right structure and tool in the process of making policy and decision. He suggested education, communication, selfish devotion, tolerance, statesmanship and a burning sense of humour in managing the nation’s resources. If applies to all organization too. It will be part of benefits. From the foregoing views by various scholars, it can be adduced that leaders are given direction and they work towards achievement of goals and objectives. To head or direct is to step ahead showing the way for others to follow, not probing the group from

behind. This implies that the leader determines the group of objectives to be accomplished, influences (motivates) after communicating what and how the goal may be achieved, and oversees (supervises) the group efforts to achieve the set goals. A leader has to do with call for superior-subordinate relationship. This includes the management by objectives, which shall be seen as jointly determined and need to be pursued jointly to achieve a desired result.

QUALITIES OF A GOOD LEADER

There are common traits that define leadership, and finding them take some study of those who have successful, by actively building on those traits you can develop into a stronger leader. Here are some of the common traits in the leader characteristics of leadership.

- **Empathy:** creating a legitimate rapport with your staff makes it less likely that personal issues and resentment can creep in and derail the group. When your team knows that you are empathetic to their concerns, they will be more likely to work with you and share in your vision, than foster negative feelings.
- **Consistency:** being a consistent leader will gain you respect and credibility, which is essential to getting buy-in from the group. By setting an example of fairness and credibility, the team will want to act the same.
- **Honesty:** another characteristic of leadership that leads to credibility. Those who are honest, especially about concerns, makes it far more likely that obstacles will be addressed rather than avoided. Honesty also allows for better assessment and growth.
- **Direction:** Having the vision to break out of the norm and aim for great things- then the steps necessary to get there- is an essential characteristics of good leadership. By seeing what can be and managing the goals on how to get there, a good leader can create impressive change.
- **Communication:** Effective communication helps keep the team working on the right attitude. If you keep the team working on the right attitude. If you communicate effectively about expectations, issues and advice, your staff will be more likely to react and meet your team and reward good ideas.
- **Conviction:** A strong vision and the willingness to see it through is one of the most important characteristics of leadership. The leadership who believes in the mission and work towards it will be an inspiration and a resource to their followers “successful people maintain a positive focus in life no matter what is going on around them. They stay focused on their past successes rather than their past failures, and on next action steps they need to take to get them closer to the fulfillment of their goals rather than all the other distractions that life presents to them”- Jack canfield

TYPES OF POWER

Power has been an important aspect of human civilization since time immemorial. Power might be physical, political or social. Power basically emanates from position or authority which influences people both positively and negatively. For simplicity and understanding purposes power is usually classified into the following categories:

1. Legitimate power

Legitimate power also known as position power or official power comes to the leader when the organization’s authority is accepted. It comes from the rules of the organization. It gives leader

control resources and to reward and punish others. People accept its power because they believe that it is desirable and necessary to maintain order and discipline in a society.

2. Charismatic power

Charismatic power or power of personality comes from each leader individually. This is the power of attraction or devotion, the desire of one person to admire another. The leaders have a personal magnetism, an air of confidence and a belief in objectives that attracts and hold followers, a subordinate feels a positive attraction towards a leader by identifying himself with the leader, and this power helps the subordinate to understand and value the leader so much that he understands and acts according to the expectations of the leader. Joan of arc in France, Mahatma Gandhi and Netajisubhas in India is historical examples of charismatic leaders.

3. Expert power

Expert power comes from specialized learning, this is power of knowledge and skill of a special and that are important in getting the job done. A person's professional competence or knowledge give hi expert power. His credibility increases, he can lead other persons to trust his judgments and decisions.

4. Reward point

Reward power comes from authority; this arises from the authority to reward worthy behavior. The leader has the power to give tangible rewards such as promotion, time off from work and attractive work assignments to the subordinate. Also psychological rewards like praise, appreciation, approval and recognition can be given by the leader to the subordinate. The subordinate has to believe that he has access to higher authorities and therefore he can give rewards. The reward power can also increase the leaders' charismatic and legitimate power.

5. Coercive power

It is the ability to threaten to punish, the leader can give tangible punishments like dismissal, demotion, and low rating etc. psychological punishment includes criticism, avoidance, disapproval, satirical remarks to the subordinate. The reward power helps to avoid something undesirable, self-esteem of the subordinate increases because of reward power and decrease of punishment or coercive power.

6. Political power

This power comes from the support of a group, it arises from a leader's ability to work with people and social systems to gain their allegiance and support. It develops in all organizations. There are a number of tactics that leaders can use to gain political power. One such tactics is social exchange with implies, "if you do something for me, I will do something for you". It relies on the norm reciprocity in society where two persons in a continuing relationship feel a strong obligation to repay their social debts to each other. When these trade-offs are successful, both parties get something they want. To relate political power with the path-goal, a leader should work in collaboration with employees to help see and obtain objectives that support the overall vision of the organization.

CONCLUSION

Many theoretical concepts have been used to describe leadership. Prominent among them are the traits approach, the situation concepts and combinations traits, and the situation concept approach manifesting into group dynamics approach. The basic objectives of the study have been the determination of the impact of leadership style on achieving organizational effectiveness. Attention was also focused on the topic in creating efficiency on organizations that fully embraced effective leadership styles.

During the study, some findings were made and discussed. The research work has shown that for any organization to survive, appropriate impact of leadership styles must be adopted. It is hoped that the presentation of leadership in this project will contribute to the better understanding of the need for adopting of democratic, participative leadership in an organization, which will enhance organizational effectiveness. It is inferred that democratic or participative types of leadership is the best of all the leadership styles because of the benefits that will be derived from it by the employees amid the overall result to the organization as a whole

Suggestions

Having x-rayed the efficacy of effective leadership in organisations for performance and productivity, the following suggestions are adjudged:

1. Quality leaders should always be saddled with organizational responsibilities;
2. Incentive and motivation are very important tools for inducing performance and productivity;
3. and Leaders should adopt synthetic approach which comprises all the styles of leadership.

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